

STRATEGY OF ACTION IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN, THE LEGAL BASIS FOR THE GLORIFICATION OF HUMAN DIGNITY

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Annotation: Since the strategy of action is the main guideline of our time, its implementation is as universal as any normative legal act. True, in it the obligations and tasks that apply to citizens are not clearly expressed. Basically, tasks are assigned to state authorities and civil society institutions. The strategy is seriously different from the current national programs with normative legal status adopted by the Supreme Assembly.

Keywords: Strategy, Constitution, new Uzbekistan development strategy, “human — society — state”, “call for action on the path of Human Rights”.

Reforms carried out on all fronts in Uzbekistan are becoming more dynamic. And the intended finish is clear. They are fully reflected in the strategy of actions in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017 — 2021, approved by the decree of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated February 7, 2017. According to the legal nature and legal status of this document, Uzbekistan has become completely new in the field of law-making. Therefore, it is of great importance to study and understand it, first of all, clearly and fully. In order to fulfill this task, propaganda groups consisting of famous scientists and specialists were organized, which conducted scientific and practical seminars throughout the territory of our country. This process continues consistently in places even now. It should be said that the draft document was developed on the basis of the issues, opinions and demands of the population raised during the presidential election meetings during the dialogue with the people. In addition, its discussion was held with the participation of the general public, experts, with the use of internet capabilities to be thorough. Foreign specialists also took an active part in this process. More than a thousand proposals and recommendations were expressed in this way. This means that the action strategy project has passed a nationwide discussion, which is an important democratic value. After all, the measures, changes and updates expressed in this document are a reflection of the will, desire and interests of the people. Consequently, as defined in our Constitution, the people are one and the same source of state power. This is also

the main reason why he was warmly welcomed and warmly supported by our people. Although, the strategy of action is not called law, it is a normative legal act that has supreme legal force. On the basis of the organizational and legal measures outlined in it, the goals of increasing the welfare of the people, raising the potential of the state and society in accordance with the requirements of today's globalization process and the world market situation are embodied. To achieve this, the strategy sets out the principles of the next five years of development, which apply to the state as well as society. Among them, it is possible to constantly modernize the state and society, strengthen the system of internal and external competitiveness, liberalize public administration in favor of the functions of society, strengthen the communication activities of state bodies with the people, improve the mechanisms of ensuring human rights and freedoms, as well as legitimate interests, and highlight other principles.

Since the strategy of action is the main guideline of our time, its implementation is as universal as any normative legal act. True, in it the obligations and tasks that apply to citizens are not clearly expressed. Basically, tasks are assigned to state authorities and civil society institutions. The strategy is seriously different from the current national programs with normative legal status adopted by the Oliy Majlis. First of all, national programs will be adopted without a nationwide discussion, aimed only at the development of one industry or another. The execution of action strategies imposes duties not on one legislative body, but on the entire network of state power. Of course, it should focus more on one of the main principles of the legal state — the rule of law, that is, the adoption of new laws and the adoption of work based on the laws, the observance of which is defined as the main issue. The strategy of action is a legal guideline, which does not consist of dry ideas and instructions, but covers specific execution mechanisms, reflects practical measures. It clearly defines what needs to be done in order to carry out the specified activities in practice, such as the adoption of a special law or the development and approval of a state program or the implementation of construction, re-equipment and creation, etc. Suppose that in the strategy of action there is a conceptual rule about the development of private partnerships with the state. In order to ensure the implementation of this rule, the state program for 2017, aimed at implementing the strategy, provides for the adoption of the law “on public and private partnership”. Speaking about the legal nature and significance of the action strategy, another of its highlights is that it is intended for the next five years. It is known that in foreign countries there is a practice of developing strategic documents for 10 years, 20 years and even

more. However, in foreign experience, it is common to accept such documents for the term of office of the head of state, and this is considered logical. Because in the current period when the world is developing with shitob, it is very difficult to set a goal for the long term. So, since the state and society have so great heights in the socio-political and economic-cultural spheres, what should we, our citizens' duties and responsibilities consist of? These should be reflected, first of all, in working in a new way and living in a new way. We must be representatives of such qualities as business and entrepreneurship. Consequently, we are absolutely not mistaken, if we say that the strategy of action is a legal guarantee of achieving high progress. Speaking about the meaning and essence of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan, it should be noted its historical significance, which is manifested in the following three levels.

The first is the importance of the new Uzbekistan development strategy at the national level. A thorough analysis of the priorities and the most important tasks set in the development strategy shows that the new

A completely new national legal system is being formed in Uzbekistan. That is, the principle of "Man, his rights, freedoms, especially value — the highest value" is recognized.

The principle of "State — Society — man", which has been in force for years in the new Uzbek development strategy, is being changed to the principle of "Man — society — state". To put it more simply, in Uzbekistan there is an emphasis on the need to raise the value and improve the well-being of every citizen.

The main thing is to ensure human dignity — the main idea of the 7 priority directions in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan. Because the main idea in the election program of our president was also the principle "for human dignity".

How to implement the imposition of human dignity in legal and organizational and legal ways at the levels of national, regional and international cooperation in all spheres of our life? In the development strategy, there are practical answers to this pressing question, aimed at many specific goals.

The second is the importance of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan at the regional level. For the purposes envisaged in the development strategy, special attention is paid to the important tasks of valuing close brotherhood between the peoples of Central Asia, strengthening beneficial cooperation with neighboring countries, achieving regional security and sustainable development.

The third is the importance of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan at the international (global) level. The development strategy spoke about strengthening

activities in UN bodies and institutions, global and regional economic, financial and humanitarian organizations, in particular, raising international cooperation to a new level in solving global problems such as climate, ecology, terrorism, corruption, migration, poverty.

That is, it is necessary to consistently continue the instructive practice associated with the widespread introduction of Uzbekistan to the world community through UN structures. Of particular importance is the provision of implementation of initiatives of the leadership of Uzbekistan within the framework of the UN, the development of economic, financial and consultative cooperation with the UN and its institutions.

The development strategy also shows the prospects for continuing close cooperation with all partners in order to accelerate cultural and humanitarian cooperation with the UN and its specialized institutions, to promote the UN initiative “call for action for Human Rights”.

At this point, not only the naming of the new Uzbekistan development strategy, but also the priorities and important tasks set in it are in harmony and harmony with international documents of great importance not only at the national or regional level, but also at the global level.

At first, in the strategy of action, and now in the development strategy, a clear national program for the implementation of the goals of Sustainable Development by the UN, which Uzbekistan undertakes to fulfill, was determined.

In other words, Uzbekistan, as an equal member of foreign international relations, was able to show the whole world its unique role and importance in this regard, and more importantly, its exemplary experience, developing in harmony with the goals of sustainable development of the UN. In turn, the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan indicates that this important progressive process is continuing without interruption.

Today, a draft Convention on the right to progress is being developed by the international community. In addition, the declaration on the right to progress has been in effect for 35 years. In this sense, the development strategy presented by the president of Uzbekistan fully corresponds to the development trends of the international community, the development trends of the whole world.

Development strategy of New Uzbekistan: assessment of international and foreign experts

The development strategy of the New Uzbekistan is of great interest to partner foreign countries and international organizations, the entire world community. In recognition of the comprehensive and fierce reforms carried out by a number of

influential foreign and international experts at the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in Uzbekistan, the project of this new historical document has received high marks, and we will focus on some of them.

The special rapporteur of the UN Human Rights Council, who visited our country on November 28-December 7, 2021, on the issues of promoting and protecting human rights in the fight against terrorism Fionnuala, highly appreciated our efforts to return citizens to the country, rehabilitation and reintegration, in particular, within the framework of Operation "Mehr", recognizing that Aolayn is a leader in the

The secretary general of the Inter-Parliamentary Union Martin Chungong made a statement about the full support of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's international initiatives aimed at increasing the role of national parliaments. At this point, the head of State:

first, the adoption of a special resolution of the UN General Assembly on strengthening the role of parliaments in the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals and the protection of human rights;

secondly, to hold the World Summit of women-speakers in Uzbekistan this year; thirdly, initiatives aimed at stimulating initiatives for the development of youth parliaments and establishing close cooperation in this regard are envisaged.

In turn, the president of the Geneva diplomatic circles, Robert Blum, noted that the new initiatives to protect the rights of private property and entrepreneurs promoted by the president of Uzbekistan, to stimulate the private sector, will lead to economic growth of the country and an increase in the welfare of the population.

And the editor-in-chief of the International Magazine Diva International, Marit Foss, drew attention to the fact that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev positions himself as a full-fledged Democrat. The international expert noted that the main goal of the president of Uzbekistan is to ensure human dignity. This, in turn, means the protection of human rights. It is a correct and rational way that a policy of decentralization is being pursued in the country, that is, some important powers of the central state bodies are transferred to local authorities.

According to the French online publication Newly, the development strategy of New Uzbekistan will begin a new stage in the national development of the country. In particular, the priority principle "man — Society — state" becomes an important criterion for a radical change in the social environment in society.

As a result of listening to the speech of the head of state about the prospects for the implementation of the state program on the implementation of the new Uzbek

development strategy in the year of “honor of human dignity and active neighborhood”, we also had a number of thoughts. It is not for nothing that the president paid special attention to the need to widely promote the content of the state program in order to fully fulfill it and give it the expected effect.

To this end, at the national level: at all stages of education from schools to higher educational institutions, we offer to hold a national essay competition on the book “strategy of New Uzbekistan”. This event serves to strengthen the ideas of patriotism, national pride in the consciousness of our youth and the formation of strong ideological immunity. At the international level: it is necessary to conduct an international forum in the form of a hybrid on the topic “New Uzbekistan development strategy”. The organization of various political-diplomatic events in the same direction is also a term. In conclusion, the processes of consistent implementation of the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan began on the date when Shavkat Mirziyoyev officially took over the post of President of Uzbekistan for the second time. In the meantime, over the past 80 days, 6 laws, 7 presidential decrees and 17 decisions were adopted. At this point, it is worthwhile to highlight new laws “on the state of emergency”, “on the establishment of the day of entrepreneurs”, “on insurance activities”, adopted at the direct initiative of the head of state, and important amendments to a number of laws. All these legislative acts, which are consistently introduced into practice today, are aimed at the unconditional fulfillment of the priorities and the most important tasks set out in the development strategy.

At the moment, we have a huge range of tasks, such as the thoughtful promotion of the meaning and significance of the new Uzbek development strategy, the implementation of the important tasks set in it, analysis and monitoring of its implementation.

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